

Sequential Monte Carlo for CBM+ Using TensorFlow

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Abstract

As the Department of Defense (DoD) aims to become more efficient, condition-based maintenance (CBM⁺) is an expected support capability of modern systems. CBM⁺ model selection depends largely on available data. This data commonly includes historical maintenance and failure events, state observations from sensors of instrumented systems, manufacturer specifications, and system tests (e.g., highly accelerated life tests (HALT)). Physics-driven state-space models may be selected to address CBM⁺ on highly reliable systems due to the method's ability to leverage state observations and HALT. However, such models are time-intensive to develop and computationally demanding to simulate.

To minimize development time, computational packages for constructing physics-driven state-space simulations have been built. However, existing packages tend to target research groups and often do not take advantage of distributed computing capabilities available in deployed settings. Addressing this need, Northrop Grumman has developed a package extending TensorFlow for component modeling and probabilistic prediction of Remaining Useful Life (RUL) to inform CBM⁺ through physics-driven state-space models. This package provides sufficient generality and application of finite difference methods, sequential Monte Carlo filters, Monte Carlo (MC) simulation, and Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods allowing for a consistently deployable framework with the option to tailor elements of the implementation as needed. In this paper, we discuss the methods and package architecture that enable the translation of telemetry and HALT data to RUL prediction and model deployment on a production architecture enabling optimized CBM⁺ on DoD systems.

Key Words: Bayesian, state-space, forecasting, software packages, reliability, prognostics, condition-based maintenance, remaining useful life

1. Introduction

The Department of Defense (DoD) has a critical stake in decreasing life cycle costs over a systems life cycle. According to the (DoD) guide book on condition-based maintenance plus (CBM⁺) (Bell, 2008) Operations & Support costs account for 65-80% of total life cycle costs (see Figure 1).

To illustrate the magnitude of costs, the DoD estimates the F-35 joint strike fighter program costs will be nearly \$1.7 trillion over its life cycle, of which over \$1.3 trillion is expected to apply to operations and support (DC, 2020). To minimize these costs, the DoD seeks to apply transformational technologies within the CBM⁺ space (Bell, 2008). Broadly, CBM⁺ is “the application and integration of appropriate processes, technologies, and knowledge-based capabilities to improve reliability and maintenance effectiveness of DoD systems and components (Bell, 2008).”

One way to minimize costs in CBM⁺ applications is to adopt a prognostics modeling library to support data scientists in making model development and deployment as seamless and efficient as possible. In Python, the ecosystem of modeling packages is vast. We narrow the search in this paper to a subset of those packages that support CBM⁺ applications for high-criticality systems that require high precision physic-based models. Along the way,

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Figure 1: DoD system lifecycle costs by phase .

we describe why sequential Monte Carlo methods are ideal for this model paradigm. We then consider several Python packages that support this type of model development. Using a simple framework (Figure 3) for describing the trade-offs that developers make in creating these solutions, we illustrate advantages and disadvantages that these packages have in model development and deployability in a commercial CBM⁺ modeling framework.

2. Why Sequential Monte Carlo for CBM⁺

Modern machine learning shows great promise in CBM⁺ applications (Jardine, Lin, & Banjevic, 2006; Sharma, Mittal, & Soni, 2022; Coraddu et al., 2016). However, these methods often require vast amounts of data for model training and validation. The requirement for large quantities of data can be problematic in both legacy systems and yet-to-be-fielded modern systems.

For instance, legacy defense data collection practices were not designed with machine learning applications in mind. These data may consist of physical sensor data and/or maintenance records containing failures and other relevant information. Since these systems are highly reliable, there is rarely sufficient failure data to support training of machine learning models. For example, it is common to observe highly imbalanced data, i.e., few failure examples in contrast to many non-failures (Dewey & DeVries, 2021). Moreover, the scarce data that exists frequently suffers from reliability issues through poorly designed data collection practices. To overcome these limitations, simple Bayesian models with priors based on manufacturer specifications have been used successfully. However, the gross estimates for system failure provided by these methods are insufficient for high criticality components.

In the case of a system that has yet-to-be-fielded, physical sensor data and failure data are absent for use as targets in a machine-learning training regime. Again, these systems are highly reliable, so even when physical sensor data becomes available, it may be decades before associated failure data is collected. One way to address these limitations is to use well-developed deterministic physical models and information about the intended use of the system to simulate both physical sensor data and associated failures leading to RUL estimates in different scenarios (Sojourner et al., 2015; Dewey, DeVries, & Hyde, 2019). However, such models do not allow for updating of RUL estimates through incorporation of on-line sensor data once the system is fielded.

These sensor data provide a view into the continuous operation of the system and seem to provide optimal training data for machine learning algorithms, particularly if the sensors collect data directly related to the degradation mechanisms of the systems. However, as mentioned previously, there are rarely enough failure observations to associate with sensor

data. Moreover, sensors that collect data directly related to degradation mechanisms are often destructive. For example, build-up of oppositely charged ions at the anode and cathode of a lithium-ion battery is a prime failure mechanism, but measuring this requires the battery to be opened, which then makes the battery unusable in the long term.

Despite the difficulties of modeling highly reliable systems in the above circumstances, the inefficiencies, excess costs, and unacceptable system unavailability require estimates of system and component RUL. To this end, we consider the use of sequential Monte Carlo methods for modeling system and component RUL.

Sequential Monte Carlo (SMC) methods are useful in reliability modeling due to their ability to incorporate system physical constraints, model unmeasurable (i.e., hidden) states, and provide greater precision in remaining useful life models (Lucu, Martinez-Laserna, Gandiaga, & Camblong, 2018). Moreover, in complete absence of data, the deterministic equations that describe a system’s state and information about the intended system use patterns may be used to simulate data, which may then be used in SMC to directly estimate system RUL. However, in contrast to machine learning methods, SMC is complex and requires a well developed framework providing a multitude of algorithm choices at each stage of the overall process. The Northrop Grumman CBM⁺ team found a number of existing packages with great support and documentation. However, these packages were designed to foster research, and lack the functionality required for scalable deployed systems.

Sequential Monte Carlo is composed of a state-space model (i.e., sufficiently transformed differential equations) and a filtering algorithm (e.g., Kalman Filter or particle filter) (Chopin, Papaspiliopoulos, et al., 2020). Historically, SMC was used to solve partial differential equations in the form of Feynman-Kac path integration problems. Nicolas Chopin (Nchopin, n.d.) developed an SMC package built with this historical viewpoint in mind. More recently, SMC has been used in control theoretic settings including robotics for geolocation. These applications tend to focus on short-term predictions.

In contrast, applications to reliability often require long-term predictions. NASA AMES developed a prognostics models package that extends SMC functionality to account for longer-term predictions in prognostic health management (Teubert, Corbetta, Kulkarni, Jarvis, & Daigle, 2022; Teubert, Corbetta, & Kulkarni, 2022). The author notes the great support provided by NASA for their package, which was ultimately used as inspiration for the development of the internal Northrop Grumman package written in TensorFlow.

3. SMC with MC Specification

This section develops SMC for estimating remaining useful life (RUL). Following the development of Doucet (Doucet, De Freitas, Gordon, et al., 2001) and Dahlin (Dahlin & Schön, 2019), we give a concise mathematical development of SMC. We then extend standard SMC to forecasting RUL following Daigle & Kulkarni (Daigle & Kulkarni, 2016).

3.1 Sequential Monte Carlo

Sequential Monte Carlo methods are composed of a state-space model representing a stochastic process and a filtering method used to estimate hidden states based upon related observed data. In the case of CBM⁺, the state-space model is generally a system of differential equations describing a deterministic physical system. Noise parameters are injected to account for variation in the physical process due to unaccounted-for external inputs and variation due to sensors that measure a subset of the physical attributes of the system.

Since we are modeling the state of the system in time, we use t indices to represent time. The measurable states (\mathbf{y}_t) of the system are observed variables. The unmeasurable states

Figure 2: Hidden Markov model representation of a sequential Monte Carlo model.

(\mathbf{x}_t), or so-called hidden states, may not generally be directly accessible. For example, refer to the earlier battery example, where measuring ion build-up results in the destruction of the battery. Hence, ion build-up is a hidden state captured only indirectly through the system of differential equations that describe the battery degradation process. See (Daigle & Kulkarni, 2016) for a detailed example. Abstractly, Figure 2 shows the canonical diagram for a hidden Markov model with the Markov kernel and likelihood included to connect the two representations. The goal being to estimate the hidden states (\mathbf{x}_t) using information gained through observed data (\mathbf{y}_t). This is the goal of estimation in an SMC model and the hidden Markov model provides a high level view of this goal.

The specification of the state-space model used in an SMC algorithm designed to estimate \mathbf{x}_t and \mathbf{y}_t is given by

$$\mathbf{x}_0 \sim \mu_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_0), \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{x}_{t-1} \sim f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{x}_{t-1}), \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{x}_t \sim g_{\theta}(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{x}_t). \quad (3)$$

The distribution (1) 1 is the prior distribution of the hidden state. This is often informed by manufacturer specifications (e.g., a battery's initial count of lithium ions). The distribution (2) 2 is the Markov kernel or transition distribution, and distribution (3) 3 is the likelihood of the observed data at time t , given the estimated hidden state. The functions μ , f , and g are the relevant densities and are dependent on the parameter vector θ , which may or may not be fixed. If θ is not fixed, then it must be estimated. Common options for this estimation include Markov chain Monte Carlo or stochastic variational inference.

In many use-cases, the goal of SMC is to estimate the hidden state given observations and no forecasting is applied. In these cases, the following relationships

$$p(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{y}_{1:t-1}) = \int f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{x}_{t-1}) p(\mathbf{x}_{t-1} | \mathbf{y}_{1:t-1}) d\mathbf{x}_{t-1}, \quad (4)$$

$$p(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{y}_{1:t}) = \frac{g_{\theta}(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{x}_t) p(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{y}_{1:t-1})}{\int g_{\theta}(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{x}_t) p(\mathbf{x}_t | \mathbf{y}_{1:t-1}) d\mathbf{x}_t} \quad (5)$$

are used to obtain the prediction (Eqn. 4) and the subsequent correction (Eqn. 5) to the hidden state based upon the latest observed data.

Estimating RUL, however, requires a long-term forecast. Extending Equations 4 and 5, we fix the parameters using the last available observed data and using Monte Carlo integration we project forward from time t to time $t + \tau$ using Equation 6 below.

$$p(\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau}|\mathbf{y}_{1:t}) = \int f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau}|\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau-1})p(\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau-1}|\mathbf{y}_{1:t}) d\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau-1}, \quad (6)$$

$$p_{\text{failure}}(\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau}) = \int p(\text{failure}|\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau-1}, \text{lb}, \text{ub})p(\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau-1})d\mathbf{x}_{t+\tau-1}. \quad (7)$$

Finally, Equation 7 may be used to estimate system RUL, given a lower bound (lb) and upper bound (ub) on acceptable values of the system’s hidden state.

4. Existing Sequential Monte Carlo Python Packages

The desired functionality from a modeling package is to support rapid development of prototype models with the ability to transition to production models, and support model deployment to production environments. To meet this goal, developers use their own experience, research, business needs, and collaboration with others to know which level and domain of abstraction might be useful to users. As noted in (Bingham et al., 2019) regarding the development of probabilistic programming languages, “...in conventional programming language development... design decisions are not universally applicable or desirable... and that other systems purposefully make different tradeoffs to achieve different goals.” Below we show that this behavior extends more broadly to numerical packages.

Figure 3: The three axes along which modeling libraries may be abstracted. Ultimately the architecture for any library makes trade-offs in abstraction along these axes.

In an attempt to address the motivations behind these purposeful tradeoffs, we introduce a simple framework we call the Data Science Axes of Abstraction (see Figure 3). The three axes represent domains that impose constraints on package development, namely, the business domain, application domain, and mathematical domain. The business domain includes elements like cost-benefit analysis and the need to move analytical models from the

research phase to a production setting, where possibly thousands of models churn through many terabytes of data. The application domain includes various applications that a library may support. This can be as narrow as SMC or as broad as time-series analysis. The mathematical domain represents the many possible structures that support computation. For example, something as simple as matrix multiplication has many implementations. Algorithm choice depends on the scale, sparsity, and other characteristics of the data being multiplied. One may choose to make all these implementations available, but this may violate the cost-benefit constraint in the business domain.

We have observed that need drives development further down one of the Data Science Axes of Abstraction during package development. For example, the Particles Python package developed by Chopin (Nchopin, n.d.) chose to adopt the Feynman-Kac representation of state-space models because it offers the greatest level of mathematical generality for SMC. The package author, being an expert in the field, supports a research agenda in that direction (Chopin, 2004, 2002). This library is intended to be a research library and its development is furthest down the mathematical and application domains of the Data Science Axes of Abstraction. In contrast, (Teubert et al., 2023) at the NASA AMES Prognostics Center of Excellence follow a more control theoretic approach to defining linear state-space models in their ProgPy Python package. This places some restrictions on modeling possibilities. However, the NASA packages specifically address CBM⁺ applications, as this is their charter. Finally, we note that ProgPy also attends to deployment by providing a lightweight REST API through their `prog_server` and `prog_client` libraries. The NASA packages offer much of the functionality needed in an SMC library for CBM⁺ applications. ProgPy appears furthest down the axes of application and business, but the developers note that “the package is intended to be used as a research tool to prototype and benchmark Prognostics As-A-Service (PaaS) architectures and work on the challenges facing such architectures, including Generality, Communication, Security, Environmental Complexity, Utility, and Trust” (Teubert et al., 2023). It is not intended to be used as a production modeling library. Though Particles and ProgPy may help industry better understand the needs of deploying SMC models in a production setting, neither satisfy the necessary constraints required in such settings. Moreover, these options also lack the flexibility to change modeling regimes in the face of new use-cases that may require different methodologies. For this reason, more general computational tools containing some level of probabilistic programming and the ability to scale to production were considered.

5. Probabilistic Programming Languages and SMC on TensorFlow

Modern machine learning workflows are increasingly turning to deep learning frameworks, which were originally designed for neural networks. The reasons for adopting deep learning frameworks are mostly centered around scalability and portability. This is due to native parallel processing, graph optimization, and compilation which also allows for portability to different programming language frameworks (Abadi et al., 2016; Goldsborough, 2016). Implementation of these optimization techniques are not more broadly available in base Python or Numpy. Of course, this comes with a tradeoff, but new advances are frequently made to address limitations. For example, challenges in the development of models due to lazy execution in TensorFlow resulted in the addition of eager execution as a default setting in TensorFlow. (Agrawal et al., 2019).

A major contribution to these frameworks is the addition of probabilistic programming packages that ease development of models beyond neural networks. These include Pyro built on PyTorch and TensorFlow Probability and Edward built on TensorFlow. TensorFlow and PyTorch enjoy the greatest level of support, so we do not consider the several other

options that exist.

Probabilistic programming packages built on deep learning frameworks increase the efficiency with which data scientists may create modeling products. They do this by being expressive, scalable, flexible, and minimal (Bingham et al., 2019). These attributes allow developers to conduct relatively rapid research and prototyping that can quickly be turned around into production-ready modeling products. This addresses all three axes of abstraction. However, this comes at a development cost that may not be feasible depending on the use-case. Further research may quantify the cost trade-off of development in these languages to more traditional approaches.

Ultimately we opted to build a library using the TensorFlow ecosystem. We chose this over the PyTorch ecosystem due to a seeming consensus that TensorFlow is more performant for production environments due to the static nature of the computation graphs and other implementation details. However, Pyro appears to be an equally robust solution, though we do not review it here.

Using TensorFlow and TensorFlow Probability we built a library inspired by NASA's ProgPy. The flexibility and scalability of the TensorFlow ecosystem allowed us to leverage the scientific research that went into developing NASA's ProgPy to create robust structures that address CBM⁺ specific use-cases, but also allows for production deployments. It also allows the freedom to seamlessly extend into different modeling regimes other than SMC. Moreover, leveraging the more general probabilistic programming language allows for pivoting to different implementations for the various numerical algorithms that may be useful in SMC or other modeling regimes.

Although TensorFlow and TensorFlow probability provide a production environment for model construction, there are some challenges in using the platform. The two main challenges we discuss here are debugging both hardware and code.

In the former case, the TensorFlow team has made some strides in making it easier to leverage GPU and TPU instances, which is necessary for the full performance gains offered by the platform, but there are still challenges here. Specifically, the interaction between versioning in Python, TensorFlow, and the GPU/TPU drivers. This is particularly challenging if air-gapped environments where some versions may be restricted.

Debugging code is also a challenge. Often stack trace messages are at best cryptic. Most often our experience is that tensor shape tends to be the problem, even if it is not obvious from the stack trace. There may be relief for debugging TensorFlow code with the recent release of Python 3.11. Specifically, a new Python standard PEP 657 provides "Fine-Grained Error Locations in Tracebacks," which may allow the TensorFlow team to provide better error traceability in the future.

Despite the above challenges, our experience with TensorFlow and TensorFlow probability have been positive and we will continue to develop in this framework.

6. Conclusion

CBM⁺ enables maintenance based on evidence of need and sequential Monte Carlo methods enable powerful predictions when the need arises. Building, parameterizing, and validating prognostic physics-based state space models for complex components is difficult and a well structured software library provides both a template and resources to develop models. If the end-goal is to develop a large number of production ready models that will be trained on large data sets, then a probabilistic programming language like TensorFlow probability or Pyro will meet these needs. Moreover, these languages allow for flexibility to pivot to other modeling regimes in a production-ready way. If, on the other hand, the goal is one-off models in a research environment, then an existing SMC package may be better suited.

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